

SEMI-AUTOMATIC MELODY EXTRACTION USING NOTE ONSET TIME AND PITCH INFORMATION FROM USERS

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ABSTRACT

Automatic melody extraction from music audio has proven to be challenging. In this paper we focus on semi-automatic melody extraction, where prior information produced by the user is used in the algorithm. Our experiment shows that users – even without a musical background – are able to produce useful approximations of both the note onset times and the pitches in the melody that is being extracted. We present a dynamic programming algorithm that takes this user-generated information and uses it for melody extraction. The algorithm is based on audio samples that are built around approximate note onset times. In addition to this, approximate note pitches can be used to constrain the set of possible melodies. We compare our algorithm with a state-of-the-art melody extraction algorithm using orchestral music material. In the evaluation we use simulated note approximations that could have been produced by a user without a musical background. In this setting, the accuracy of our algorithm is remarkably better than that of the automatic algorithm.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the automatic melody extraction problem, the input is an excerpt from a musical work as an audio signal, and the output is a symbolic representation of the most important melody line in the excerpt. Practical applications for automatic melody extraction include the construction of datasets for music search engines and sheet music production for individual pieces.

Automatic melody extraction is a difficult problem [1]. The difficulties lie in recognizing which frequencies in the audio signal are fundamental frequencies of musical notes and furthermore, which of the notes belong to the melody. Human listeners can easily follow different instruments and they have previous knowledge about melody structure. It is difficult to transmit these skills to a computer.

Most melody extraction systems share a common structure [4, 11, 14]. First, potential melody frequencies are filtered from the audio signal. After this, the melody is constructed using knowledge about the properties of typical melodies. Another popular approach to melody ex-

traction has been separation of melody and accompaniment sources [2, 9]. More information of the proposed melody extraction systems can be found in [13, 15].

In this paper, we concentrate on semi-automatic melody extraction. To facilitate the melody extraction from the audio signal, a semi-automatic system uses additional musical information given by the user. First we study what kind of information can be gathered from users, both with and without a musical background. After that, we present and evaluate a melody extraction algorithm that uses this information.

Of course, semi-automatic systems have severe limitations compared to independent systems. They cannot be used to automatically process large datasets because they require user interaction. However, an important use case is the transcription of an individual piece for which there is no sheet music available. In this case, it may be acceptable for the user to take a significant amount of time to help the system produce the final transcription.

User information has already been used in some signal separation systems. For example, users can provide information about instruments playing the melody [6], give a partial transcription [7] or select the audio source corresponding to the melody [3]. In Songle [5], a first draft for the transcription is produced automatically, and after that the users can work on it collaboratively.

The organization of the rest of the paper is as follows: In Section 2 we study the ability of the users to recognize note onset times and the pitches in the melody. In Section 3 we present a semi-automatic melody extraction algorithm which uses approximate note onset times and the pitches produced by the user. In Section 4 we evaluate our algorithm and compare it with a state-of-the-art automatic melody extraction algorithm. Finally, in Section 5 we present our conclusions.

2. NOTE APPROXIMATIONS

We conducted an experiment where human listeners approximated note onset times and the pitches in the melody. The experiment shows that users can produce useful onset time and pitch approximations for semi-automatic melody extraction. Our melody extraction algorithm in Section 3 is based on these approximations. We also use the results of the experiment for estimating error distribution in the evaluation of the algorithm in Section 4.

Figure 1. The Star Wars melody in the first task.

Figure 2. The Parsifal melody in the second task.

2.1 Experiment set-up

The experiment consisted of two tasks, both involving a short orchestral music excerpt containing a melody. The excerpt in the first task was a theme from Star Wars by John Williams (Figure 1), and the second excerpt was a theme from Wagner’s Parsifal (Figure 2). We tried to select melodies that are clear and unambiguous. Furthermore, we presumed that the first excerpt would be familiar for the participants and the second excerpt would be unfamiliar.

We had 30 participants in our experiment. Group A consisted of 15 participants without a musical background. Those participants either had no experience playing an instrument or singing, or had only practiced music for a short period of time during their childhood. Group B consisted of 15 participants with a strong musical background who had practiced music actively for a long time. All the participants were university students, and none of the them were professional musicians or experienced transcribers.

Figure 3 shows the user interface used in the experiment. The window is divided into two parts: the upper part contains a spectrogram of the audio file and the lower part contains a staff line with the melody. Initially, the staff line is empty. The system allows one to play a selected segment of the audio file or the melody in the staff line. In the latter case, the melody is synthesized using a flute-like sound. Notes can be added to the staff line by pressing a key while listening to the audio file. After this, the pitches of the notes can be adjusted and the notes can also be moved or removed.

Both tasks in the experiment consisted of three subtasks. The first subtask was to mark down the pulse of the melody by pressing a key at regular intervals. This subtask served as an introduction to the user interface. After this, the second subtask was to determine the note onset times in the melody and finally, the third subtask was to adjust the note pitches. We report the results of the latter two subtasks because they are relevant for our algorithm.

The participants were briefly told how to use the system at the beginning of the experiment. They were asked to work carefully, but were also told not to use too much time if they could not hear something easily. The participants typically used 10–30 minutes for each of the two tasks. The participants’s performance during a task was not commented on, and they had to decide themselves when they were ready.

Figure 3. The user interface used in the experiment.

Task	Group	Participants	avg σ_T	min σ_T
Star Wars	A	6	0.19	0.03
	B	13	0.08	0.03
Parsifal	A	11	0.13	0.08
	B	15	0.14	0.09

Table 1. Number of participants with no more than one extra or missing note. The average and minimum error deviation of note onset times are calculated for those participants.

The results in the Parsifal task were generally better than in the Star Wars task. This can be explained both by the nature of the melodies and by the structure of the experiment. The orchestration of the Parsifal melody is slower and lighter, which may make it easier to perceive and mark down. In addition to this, the Star Wars task was the first task in the experiment and the participants were more acquainted with the system when they started the Parsifal task.

2.2 Onset time determination

In the note onset time subtask, the participants placed notes on the staff line. The participants had to determine both the number of notes and the horizontal positions of the notes. The principal method for this was to press a key at each note while listening to the music. The participants were allowed to listen to the music an unlimited number of times and could move and remove notes afterwards.

Let t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n denote the reference note onset times measured in seconds and x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m the approximate onset times by the participant. If we assume that $n = m$, we can calculate the root mean squared error σ_T of the onset time using the formula $\sqrt{(\sum_1^n (t_k - x_k)^2)/n}$.

However, in practice, n and m may differ. For example, several participants ignored the C# note at the beginning of the Parsifal melody, probably interpreting it as a glissando. In the following, we regard a note onset time approximation as accurate if it contains the correct number of notes, or only has one extra or missing note.

Table 1 shows the numbers of participants with the correct number of notes, or just one extra or missing note. The average and minimum error deviation of these participants

Task	Group	$d = 0$	$d = 4$	$d = 7$	avg σ_P
Star Wars	A	1	2	7	2.41
	B	9	14	14	0.83
Parsifal	A	1	2	9	2.81
	B	11	12	15	0.71

Table 2. Number of participants who produced an d -approximation when $d \in \{0, 4, 7\}$. The average error is calculated for participants having a 7-approximation.

Task	Group	Intervals	Parsons code
Star Wars	A	1	2
	B	14	14
Parsifal	A	1	9
	B	11	14

Table 3. Number of participants having correct intervals and Parsons codes.

are also shown. If $n \neq m$, we calculate the error by excluding one note onset time in the data so that the error is minimized. About half of the participants in group A, and almost all in group B, produced accurate note onset time approximations.

Interestingly, in the Parsifal task the results of groups A and B are very similar to each other. This suggests that the musical background has a minor role in determining the onset times for a slow melody. Instead of this, a more important factor may be the experience in using the computer. Among the most accurate participants in this subtask were active computer gamers without any musical background.

Our melody extraction algorithm in Section 3 is based on note onset time approximations. It is important for the algorithm that the errors in Table 1 are small, ranging from 0.03 to 0.09 among the best participants without a musical background. In Section 4, we use an error deviation of 0.05 in producing evaluation material for the algorithm.

2.3 Pitch determination

In the note pitch subtask, the participants were given a template with correct note onset times. Their task was to determine a pitch for each of the notes. This was done by moving the note vertically using the keyboard while listening to the original audio file and the synthesized melody.

Musical background had a strong impact on this subtask. Most participants with a strong musical background (group B) determined the correct pitches easily. However, the participants in group A were in general unable to determine pitches accurately. Several participants commented that it was difficult to compare original and synthesized pitches because the timbre was different. This phenomenon has also been reported in previous studies [12].

Instead of exact pitches, we now focus on approximate pitches. Let c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n denote the correct pitches in the melody measured in semitones and a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n represent the approximate pitches, also in semitones, produced by the participant. Furthermore, we define a d -approxima-

tion as a sequence of pitches where the distance from the correct pitch is not more than d semitones, i.e. $|c_k - a_k| \leq d$, for every k . For example, $d = 7$ means that the pitch difference is no more than a perfect fifth. We also calculate the root mean squared error σ_P of the pitches using the formula $\sqrt{(\sum_1^n (c_k - a_k)^2)/n}$.

Table 2 shows the number of participants who produced d -approximations where $d \in \{0, 4, 7\}$ as well as the average errors of the pitches for participants with a 7-approximation. While the participants in group A could not recognize the pitches exactly, half of them produced a 7-approximation of the pitch sequence.

The intervals of consecutive pitches are another important aspect of the pitch sequence. The intervals of a pitch sequence are correct if $c_{k+1} - c_k = a_{k+1} - a_k$ for every k . Furthermore, the Parsons code is correct if the directions of the intervals are correct i.e. $c_k < c_{k+1}$ iff $a_k < a_{k+1}$, $c_k > c_{k+1}$ iff $a_k > a_{k+1}$, and $c_k = c_{k+1}$ iff $a_k = a_{k+1}$.

Table 3 shows the number of participants with the correct intervals and Parsons codes. Interval recognition was as difficult as exact pitch recognition: again only participants in group B were able to recognize correct intervals. However, in the Parsifal task, more than half of the participants produced a correct Parsons code.

Note pitch approximations can be used in our algorithm in Section 3, and they significantly enhance melody extraction results. In Section 4, we use an error deviation of 2.5 in producing evaluation material for the algorithm.

3. ALGORITHM

This section describes our melody extraction algorithm that uses musical information produced by the user. The algorithm exploits standard techniques for calculating pitch salience values for audio segments [13, 15]. However, the user information allows signal processing and dynamic programming methods that are usually not possible.

The algorithm selects relevant audio segments using the approximate note onset times, and approximate pitches can be used to constrain the search for the melody. The fundamental assumption in the algorithm is that the approximate note onset times are known beforehand. The results of Section 2 suggest that this assumption is meaningful when the user helps with the extraction.

The input of the algorithm consists of an audio file and the approximate note onset times retrieved from the user. As in Section 2.2, the sequence t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n denotes the note onset times. Each value t_k is the time in seconds where the k th note begins.

The algorithm assigns a pitch p_k for each note onset time. Each pitch is a note number in semitones, and it can be calculated from the note frequency f using the formula $12 \log_2(f/27.5)$. Then, for example, the note number of $A = 440$ Hz is 48, and the interval between pitches p_a and p_b is $|p_a - p_b|$ semitones.

3.1 Signal processing

The usual first step in melody extraction algorithms is to divide the audio signal into small frames that have a constant

length. After that, a frequency spectrum for each frame is calculated using the Fourier transform or a similar method. However, our algorithm uses a different approach because the note onset times are available.

For each note onset time t_k the algorithm calculates the Fourier transform of the window $[t_k + w_1, t_k + w_2]$. The idea is to select the values w_1 and w_2 so that in the resulting window the frequencies of the melody are strong. If $t_k + w_2 > t_{k+1}$, the window is $[t_k \dots t_{k+1}]$. We evaluate different ways for selecting the parameters in Section 4.

After this, the algorithm calculates a salience value $s_{k,p}$ for each note onset time t_k and pitch p . The salience values will be used in the second phase of the algorithm, and the objective is that pitches with large salience values are strong candidates for melody pitches.

Let $a_{k,f}$ be the normalized amplitude of frequency f in the Fourier transform of note onset time t_k using linear interpolation. The algorithm calculates the salience value $s_{k,p}$ as a weighted sum of the harmonics [8] by the formula

$$s_{k,p} = \sum_{i=1}^n a_{k,if(p)} h_i \quad (1)$$

where $f(p) = 27.5 \cdot 2^{p/12}$ and h_i is the weight of the i th harmonics and n is the total number of harmonics. In this paper we use the values $n = 3$ and $h_i = 1/i$.

Note that we assume that the tuning is near $A = 440$ Hz and does not change during the excerpt. This is a realistic assumption in orchestral music that we focus on.

3.2 Dynamic programming

The melody selection procedure of our algorithm is based on dynamic programming. The salience value of a pitch sequence p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n is the sum $\sum_{i=1}^n s_{i,p_i}$ of the individual salience values.

The algorithm selects a pitch sequence with a maximum salience value using the following recursive formula:

$$v_{k,p} = \begin{cases} -\infty & \text{if } p \notin P_k \\ s_{k,p} & \text{if } k = 1 \\ s_{k,p} + \max_{r \in N_{k-1,p}} v_{k-1,r} & \text{if } k > 1 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Here $v_{k,p}$ is the maximum salience value of a pitch sequence for note onset times t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k whose last pitch is p . The set P_k contains the possible values for p_k . Correspondingly, the set $N_{k,p}$ contains the possible values for p_k when p_{k+1} equals p . The construction of sets P_k and $N_{k,p}$ is the topic of Section 3.3.

The values $v_{k,p}$ can be computed efficiently using dynamic programming. Now $\max_{p \in P_n} v_{n,p}$ is the maximum salience value for the pitch sequences that satisfy the constraints given by sets P_k and $N_{k,p}$. The pitch sequence with maximum salience can be constructed in reverse order: first set $p_n = \arg \max_{p \in P_n} v_{n,p}$ and then for $k < n$, select p_k so that $v_{k,p_k} + s_{k+1,p_{k+1}} = v_{k+1,p_{k+1}}$.

3.3 Constraints

The sets P_k and $N_{k,p}$ constrain the set of possible melodies that the algorithm can produce. Let p_{min} and p_{max} be

Dataset	Type	Excerpts	Length
Dvorak	Classical	11	319 s
Rota	Film	8	230 s
Tchaikovsky	Classical	11	335 s
Wagner	Classical	9	380 s
Williams	Film	10	348 s
Total		49	1621 s

Table 4. The material used in the evaluation. There were five datasets: three sets came from classical composers and two came from film composers.

the lowest and highest possible pitches in the melody and $P_{all} = \{p_{min}, \dots, p_{max}\}$ the set of all possible pitches.

If we do not have any constraints for the pitches, we can define the sets P_k and $N_{k,p}$ simply as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P_k &= P_{all} \\ N_{k,p} &= P_{all} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Now suppose that we have some information about the note pitches produced by the user. As in Section 2.3, let c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n be the correct pitches and a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n be the approximate pitches. There may be numerous errors in the approximate pitches. However, the results of Section 2.3 suggest that they can still be used.

First we assume that the approximate pitch sequence is a d_P -approximation i.e. $|c_k - a_k| \leq d_P$ for every k . Now it is possible to construct the set P_k as follows:

$$P_k = \{p \in P_{all} : |a_k - p| \leq d_P\} \quad (4)$$

Furthermore, if we assume that the Parsons code of the approximate pitch sequence is correct, we can construct the set $N_{k,p}$ in the following way:

$$N_{k,p} = \begin{aligned} &\{r \in P_{all} : r < p, a_k < a_{k+1}\} \cup \\ &\{r \in P_{all} : r > p, a_k > a_{k+1}\} \cup \\ &\{r \in P_{all} : r = p, a_k = a_{k+1}\} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

4. EVALUATION

In this section we evaluate our algorithm using an orchestral music collection. We also compare our algorithm with a state-of-the-art automatic melody extraction algorithm. We present the best results of the algorithms and study the impact of the parameters in our algorithm.

4.1 Material

The material used in the evaluation, as presented in Table 4, consists of 49 audio excerpts with a total length of 27 minutes. We extracted the excerpts from CD tracks into mono WAV files with a sample rate of 44,100 Hz.

The material differs from the material used in MIREX [10] in two ways. First, all the excerpts are from orchestral works, whereas most of the material in MIREX is vocal music with a light accompaniment. Second, all the excerpts are from real recordings.

To get the reference melodies, we manually annotated the melodies in the material. Each annotation consists of note onset times and pitch values. All the melodies are continuous, i.e., we interpret that there are no pauses between consecutive notes. We attempted to select melodies that are clear and unambiguous. However, there is always some subjectivity in determining the melody.

Details concerning the material and our annotations used in the evaluation are available on our website ¹.

4.2 Algorithms

We evaluated four versions of the algorithm described in Section 3. We call the different versions of the algorithm A1, A2, A3 and A4. A1 uses only note onset time information. In addition to this, A2 uses note pitch approximations, A3 uses Parsons codes and A4 uses both pitch approximations and Parsons codes.

We generated the user information in the evaluation from the reference annotations. We assumed that the number of the notes is correct and used normal distribution for simulating the user error: $N(\mu_N, \sigma_N^2)$ and $N(\mu_P, \sigma_P^2)$ denote the distributions for note onset times and pitches. We used reference onset times and pitches as means and experimented with different standard deviations. Furthermore, we set the allowed pitch difference so that $d_P = 2\sigma_P$. The Parsons codes were always correct.

This simulation is, of course, a simplification compared to the real situation. However, a large-scale experiment with real users was not possible, and we expect that, despite its limitations, the simulation sheds light on the applicability of the approach.

We compared our algorithm with MELODIA [15] which is a state-of-the-art melody extraction algorithm. MELODIA is a fully automatic system and it does not utilize user information. The parameters for MELODIA are the voicing tolerance v_M and the monophonic noise filter n_M .

As opposed to our algorithm, MELODIA produces a pitch frequency for each frame in the audio and can identify frames without melody using a negative pitch value. We converted the pitch frequencies f to note numbers using the formula $12 \log_2(f/27.5)$. Furthermore, we also interpreted the negative pitch values as melody pitches because the melodies in our material are continuous.

4.3 Results

First, we present the best results achieved by the algorithms. After this, we present the results of our algorithm using varying error deviations and window parameters.

We calculated the melody extraction accuracy using the formula l_c/l_t where l_c is the total length of segments where the output of the algorithm corresponds to the reference, and l_t is the total length of the data. The accuracy can be calculated for an excerpt, a dataset or the material as a whole. The formula is similar to the overall accuracy metric used in MIREX, except that in MIREX the accuracy is calculated frame by frame.

Dataset	A1	A2	A3	A4	M
Dvorak	0.15	0.42	0.20	0.57	0.21
Rota	0.27	0.70	0.35	0.75	0.47
Tchaikovsky	0.20	0.60	0.20	0.70	0.24
Wagner	0.26	0.52	0.32	0.62	0.41
Williams	0.33	0.62	0.39	0.70	0.32
Total	0.24	0.56	0.29	0.66	0.33

Table 5. The best results of the algorithms. The error deviations are $\sigma_N = 0.05$ and $\sigma_P = 2.5$ and all the other parameters are optimized.

$\sigma_P \backslash \sigma_N$	0	0.01	0.05	0.1	0.2	0.5
0	1.00	0.99	0.94	0.88	0.75	0.53
1	0.86	0.86	0.81	0.75	0.63	0.45
2	0.75	0.74	0.71	0.66	0.56	0.40
3	0.65	0.65	0.63	0.58	0.49	0.37
4	0.60	0.60	0.58	0.54	0.45	0.33
5	0.57	0.55	0.54	0.50	0.41	0.30

Table 6. The results of A4 for all of the material when the error deviations σ_N and σ_P change.

Table 5 shows the best results of the algorithms. For generating the user information from reference melodies, we used error deviations $\sigma_N = 0.05$ and $\sigma_P = 2.5$, which are realistic deviations based on Section 2. After this, we selected window parameters $w_1 = 0.5$ and $w_2 = 0.55$ that produced the best results on the evaluation material.

M denotes the automatic MELODIA algorithm. We chose parameters $v_M = 0.5$ and $v_F = 0$ that produced the best results on the evaluation material.

The results of A1 and A3 were equal or weaker than that of MELODIA, depending on the dataset. The results of A2 and A4, that use approximate pitch values, were substantially better. In MIREX, the overall accuracy of MELODIA was 0.70 [15] which suggests that our material is more challenging than the material used in MIREX.

Table 6 shows the results of A4 when the error deviations σ_N and σ_P change and where the window parameters are $w_1 = 0.5$ and $w_2 = 0.55$, as they were previously. It seems that accurate onset times are more important than accurate note pitches; even the results with $\sigma_P = 5$ were reasonable. As expected, the accuracy without deviation was 1.00.

Table 7 shows the results of A4 when the window parameters w_1 and w_2 change and the error deviations are $\sigma_N = 0.05$ and $\sigma_P = 2.5$, as they were previously. Here w_d is the length of the window i.e. $w_d = w_2 - w_1$. There were no big differences in the results in this case. The deviation in the onset times of the approximate notes makes it difficult to determine the window parameters.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the first part of the paper, we described an experiment in which the participants transcribed two melodies from orchestral music excerpts. As expected, most participants

¹ <http://cs.helsinki.fi/u/ahslaaks/smc13/>

$w_1 \backslash w_d$	0.05	0.1	0.25	0.5	1
0.05	0.51	0.55	0.59	0.58	0.56
0.1	0.60	0.60	0.61	0.57	0.56
0.25	0.63	0.64	0.61	0.58	0.57
0.5	0.66	0.66	0.62	0.59	0.59
1	0.63	0.63	0.61	0.58	0.58

Table 7. The results of A4 for all of the material when the window parameters w_1 and $w_d = w_2 - w_1$ change.

with a musical background were able to determine note onset times and pitches accurately. However, about half of the participants without a musical background also produced useful information about the melody, even if they could not determine note pitches exactly.

In the second part of the paper, we presented a semi-automatic algorithm for melody extraction. This algorithm is based on a dynamic programming scheme and assumes that approximate note onset times and the pitches in the melody are available. Thus, the algorithm requires help from the user to extract the melody.

The proposed algorithm is intended for users without a musical background because they can benefit from it the most. Even if they cannot determine note pitches accurately, they can provide approximations good enough for the algorithm. Constraining the range of possible pitches greatly simplifies the melody extraction problem.

When using simulated information from users without a musical background, the results of our algorithm are considerably better than that of a state-of-the-art automatic algorithm. Of course, a severe weakness in our algorithm is that it requires a lot of work on the part of the user, which limits its applicability in practice.

Our future work aims to constrain the pitch range of the melody notes by using less prior information or by limiting it automatically. One possible approach only requires the user to transcribe a subset of the notes, as in [7]. Another possibility is to assume that the approximate pitch range, i.e. the register of the melody, is known. For example, in orchestral music, it is often the case that the melody is located in the high register.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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7. REFERENCES

- [1] E. Benetos et al, “Automatic music transcription: breaking the glass ceiling,” in *Proceedings of the 13th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*, 2012.
- [2] J.-L. Durrieu et al, “Source/filter model for unsupervised main melody extraction from polyphonic audio signals,” in *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 18(3), 564–575, 2010.
- [3] J.-L. Durrieu and J.-P. Thiran, “Musical audio source separation based on user-selected F0 track,” in *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Latent Variable Analysis and Signal Separation*, 2012.
- [4] M. Goto, “A real-time music scene description system: predominant-F0 estimation for detecting melody and bass lines in real-world audio signals,” in *Speech Communication*, 43(4), 311–329, 2004.
- [5] M. Goto et al, “Songle: a web service for active music listening improved by user contributions,” in *Proceedings of the 12th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*, 2011.
- [6] H. Kirchhoff, S. Dixon and A. Klapuri, “Shift-variant non-negative matrix deconvolution for music transcription,” in *Proceedings of the 37th International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing*, 2012.
- [7] H. Kirchhoff, S. Dixon and A. Klapuri, “Multi-template shift-variant non-negative matrix deconvolution for semi-automatic music transcription,” in *Proceedings of the 13th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*, 2012.
- [8] A. Klapuri, “Multiple fundamental frequency estimation by summing harmonic amplitudes,” in *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Music Information Retrieval*, 2006.
- [9] M. Lagrange et al, “Normalized cuts for predominant melodic source separation,” in *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 16(2), 278–290, 2008.
- [10] MIREX wiki containing the Audio Melody Extraction task, <http://www.music-ir.org/mirex/wiki/>
- [11] R. Paiva, T. Mendes and A. Cardoso, “Melody detection in polyphonic musical signals: exploiting perceptual rules, note salience, and melodic smoothness,” in *Computer Music Journal*, 30(4), 80–98, 2006.
- [12] M. Pitt and R. Crowder, “The role of spectral and dynamic cues in imagery for musical timbre,” in *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, 18(3), 728–738, 1992.
- [13] G. Poliner et al, “Melody transcription from music audio: approaches and evaluation,” in *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 15(4), 1247–1256, 2007.
- [14] M. Ryyänänen and A. Klapuri, “Automatic transcription of melody, bass line, and chords in polyphonic music,” in *Computer Music Journal*, 32(3), 72–86, 2008.
- [15] J. Salamon and E. Gómez, “Melody extraction from polyphonic music signals using pitch contour characteristics,” in *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 20(6), 1759–1770, 2012.